

Physico-chemical methods used to remove MPs/NPs from drinking water

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Abbreviations: Polyethylene (PE), diallyldimethylammonium chloride (PolyDADMAC), poly(acrylonitrile) (PAN), palladium (Pd), nanoparticles tracking analysis (NTA), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), polyaluminum chloride (PACl), polyester (PES), poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), polypropylene (PP), poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA), ethylene (vinyl acetate) copolymer (PEVA), polyacrylamide (PAM).

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